

Spin Resonance Capture (SRC)

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Abstract

Spin Resonance Capture (SRC) is a system, designed and developed to identify and capture the essence of constructs with unknown infinities based on application of virtual limiters and gates.

1 Introduction to Spin Resonance Capture (SRC)

The SRC system can be used to study and understand a paradigm without physical boundaries or physical limitations. Physical realm has a definitive physical boundary, but a psychological realm has no physical boundary, the area always tends towards infinity because of inertia and will continue to do so until acted upon by an intention to mark a boundary or find a stopping point.

A paradigm without a boundary or a limitation is difficult to study because of the absence of "something" that warns or notifies a need to return for research. Also, experiencing range anxiety is very real while exploring unknown infinities.

The SRC system allows a paradigm to be studied without the hassle of getting lost or experience range anxiety during research.

1.1 Failsafe Assumption

Everything in existence (tangible or intangible) that produces a signal is in movement, the moment the movement stops and momentum ceases to exist, the existence disintegrates. A signal is only generated when the existence has a presence of oscillator(s).

In the context of a psychological realm, oscillator can be used interchangeably with intention. This oscillation is the source of the ripple, eventually giving rise to signals. The state of oscillation of an existence is referred to as spin. In any system, any existence that generates vibrations has a spin.

The usage of certain scientific terms in the SRC system are semantic and has nothing to do with calculations pertaining to STEM.

1.2 Understanding Spin

To understand spin, one must understand the TBR method, which will be later discussed in the paper.

Let's consider a system with prominent building blocks and call them a , b and c .

Upon implementing the TBR method, the measures and weights (*in the SRC system these are pseudo-weights obtained by normalizing measure, and should not be mistaken for the containment of mass of a finite entity*) of a , b and c can be changed to attain a flatline, however, one must note, that even though attaining a flatline sounds attractive, it cannot be achieved because a deficit (no matter how small), will exist in a system. The process of recognizing the deficit and the attempt to bring in a surplus in one point will cause a deficit in any other point.

Now, if we automate this change and call it a correction, to bring balance and achieve a flatline by revaluation of measures and weights, and expecting the system to maintain the same valuation in all a , b and c , the system will start correcting itself in the process of achieving equal valuation between a , b and c indefinitely.

Why deficit or surplus, and not addition or subtraction? Because the effect here is non-linear. The deficit or the surplus should always be bare minimum, close to being negligible, yet, cannot be neglected because of the tiny imbalance created in the system. High deficit or surplus signifies a collapsing system.

The blocks a , b and c cannot maintain the same value, it is impossible, no matter the size of the difference, at least one point will always fall short. Now, the self correcting system will eventually give rise to a spin, because of the activity. The self-correction of the system by the TBR method will constantly evolve and devolve based on the valuation and correction thereof. The need for alignment, resulting in maintaining a flatline, generates dynamics in a system giving rise to a spin.

1.2.1 Alignment before expectations

The above figure represents the state of alignment based on an unknow spin in it's pre-attention state.

1.2.2 Alignment after relaxation

The above figure represents the state of alignment of spin post attention.

1.3 Understanding Resonance

A resonance in this context is a highlight that signifies prominence.

A circle is divided into four quadrants.

The above figure represents division of a circle into four insignificant quadrants.

Every quadrant is a virtual sensor of known and unknown values. The known and the unknown values will always be valid.

The above figure represents division of a circle into four known insignificant quadrants and relative unknown borderless expanse. kV - known and valid, ukV - unknown and valid.

The circle is created to offer relief by avoiding infinite measure, here we don't discuss the spread of something, we discuss where something is directed.

Every quadrant functions as both a limiter and a gate depending on the changing state of the quadrant.

Limiter: A structure constructed to block something. For example, a wall in a boundary.

Gate: An opening constructed to allow something to pass through. For example, a gate in a boundary.

The above figure represents the significance of every quadrant by introducing limiters and gates. Where a , b , c and d are both passive and active limiters; and gates.

When the quadrant is in an *OFF* state, the boundary of the quadrant turns to a Passive Limiter.

The above figure represents a random alignment.

When the quadrant is in a *READY* state, the boundary turns to an Active Limiter and will be put on stand-by, anticipating an event.

The above figure represents a forced alignment.

When an event occurs, and is *CAPTURED*, the boundary of the quadrant turns to a Gate, allowing the captured data to pass through, for the purpose of documentation and study; while invalidating the remaining quadrants.

The above figure represents a decisive alignment based on proximity or affinity.

State	Behavior
OFF	Passive Limiter
READY	Active Limiter
CAPTURE	Gate

The data is captured because of the proximity or affinity only, and not the properties of the quadrants.

The data is not manipulated in the quadrants because the quadrants are simply placeholders.

The quadrants are both static and dynamic in nature; they are static by presence and dynamic by position.

In other words, they are dormant when inactive, and alive when active - because activation of a quadrant automatically activates the rest. This doesn't mean all quadrants will be functional at the same time, it just means all quadrants will be obligated to stay ready when one quadrant gets to a ready state without any travel involved.

The data passed through the gate is the captured resonance.

Philosophy - "You need all, to realize the one".

1.4 Intelligence

To make the above system work, we will redefine intelligence to suit the SRC system.

Why redefine Intelligence?

Intelligence will be redefined to serve the SRC system without introducing complexity.

- **Intelligence** is the ability to convert information to knowledge.
- **Brilliance** is the ability to convert information to useful knowledge.
- **Stupidity** is the ability to convert information to useless knowledge.
- **Idiocy** is the inability to convert information to knowledge.

Now, we further divide intelligence into proximal intelligence and affinitive intelligence.

1.4.1 Proximal Intelligence

Proximal intelligence is the ability to convert information to knowledge based on proximity.

In proximal intelligence, the conversion of information to knowledge is based on a measure or weight. This works only when we know the existence of two definite points. For example, the distance between point A and point B is 10kms, this means point A is known and so is point B.

1.4.2 Affinitive Intelligence

Affinitive intelligence is the ability to convert information to knowledge based on affinity.

In affinitive intelligence, the conversion of information to knowledge is based on undoctored tendency. This works when we know the existence of one definite point A and other arbitrary points. For example, the distance between point A and an arbitrary point B is always 0. The concept of a distance is only introduced for the sake of comprehension in relation to the proximal intelligence, but in reality, the distance simply doesn't exist or doesn't matter or is of no use while dealing with affinitive intelligence.

1.5 Alignment

Now let's derive alignments based on redefined intelligence:

1.5.1 Proximal Alignment

Proximal intelligence enables proximal alignment.

- Applies to the tangible.
- Formed.
- Can be forced.
- Can be misused, abused or neglected.
- Cannot be misunderstood.
- Short-term.
- Based on interest.

1.5.2 Affinitive Alignment

Affinitive intelligence enables affinitive alignment.

- Applies to the intangible.
- Formless.
- Cannot be forced.
- Cannot be misused, abused or neglected.
- Can be misunderstood.
- Long-term.
- Based on passion.

The alignments matter in this context because the system deals with infinity.

Philosophy - "The fed must align, if not, you are feeding the unstable."

1.5.3 Examples of alignment based on proximal and affinitive intelligence

1.

Proximal - the distance between two points A and B could be 10 million light years away.

Affinitive - the distance between the same two points A and B is 0 (always).

2.

Proximal - Five people are sitting next to each other. The fifth person is four people away from the first person. The alignment between the first person and the fifth person is a difference of three person-distance. Three person-distance is not a standard unit of measure, and should not be considered as one. To an on-looker, the alignment between first person and fifth person could mean forced distancing, avoidance, lack of closeness etc. In reality, the on-looker might be correct. The lack of closeness in space could be considered as a separation.

Affinitive - Five people are sitting next to each other. The fifth person is four galaxies away from the first person. The alignment between the first person and the fifth person is a difference of one billion star-distance. One billion star-distance is not a standard unit of measure, and should not be considered as one. To an on-looker, the alignment between first person and fifth person could mean forced distancing, avoidance, lack of closeness etc. In reality, the on-looker might be wrong. The lack of closeness in space, even though astronomical, need not hold ground because the first person and the fifth person could be in total alignment with each other.

3.

Proximal - Children learn from their parents based on exposure. Only tangible can be easily exposed.

Affinitive - What a child decides to learn is based on a feeling. Feelings can be expressed, and cannot be exposed.

Even though the above examples might be unsettling or absurd, they are possible.

The universe is set in motion because of proximity or affinity. We will further understand this while discussing the TBR method.

Every intent, every action is accompanied by an energy signature (heat) as an evidence for utilization of energy, this energy signature can be captured as heat itself, in proximity; or existence of something that cannot be explained but is prominent enough to be sensed via affinity.

1.6 Rules

1. The circle shouldn't determine the outcome.
2. The quadrants will be equally divided.
3. No quadrant will take precedence or priority.
4. Orientation or rotation of quadrants shouldn't matter.
5. The quadrants shouldn't determine the outcome.
6. The system will reset on gating, no residue will be stored.
7. The residue will be fed back into the the TBR method as entropy.

1.7 Process steps

Align \longrightarrow *Anticipate* \longrightarrow *Capture* ($|=|$)

Philosophy - "Alignment always leaves a trail."

2 The Triangulation By Reduction (TBR) Method

The TBR method is a process of reduction of parameters of interest in a paradigm to a group of three points.

After reduction, the parameters can be manipulated to obtain a result.

The goal of the TBR method is to maintain an equilibrium, a flatline on a graph.

The above figure represents a simple triangle with x , $x2$, $x3$ as the primary blocks.

The above figure represents the building blocks x , $x2$, $x3$ as non-specific Glual anchors (\mathcal{Q}).

Everything in the universe can be reduced to a two point system, where one point will always contain the priority, the second point will accommodate everything else. Since, a two point system will not provide accurate information due to the absence of accountability, a three point system will be considered.

In a two point system, the burden of carrying the remainder (entropy) falls on the point that is considered to be weaker, any dispute will be dealt with dominance and not reasoning, because of lack of accountability.

In a three point system the burden of carrying the remainder cannot be earmarked, because if one point is expected to carry the burden of the remainder, then that point can question the legitimacy of the expected carry, this creates a need for revaluation and triggers the system to self-correct.

The three point system can still be reduced to a two point system but this defeats the purpose of holding accountability, because the two point system can only exist without an accountability factor.

The above figure represents a simple triangle with three Glual anchors (Φ) and entropy (ez).

Observation 1: The presence of an accountability factor gives rise to the concept of reconciliation, eventually reducing everything to a single point or zero or a singularity. Here singularity should not be considered as empty or void, and should be considered as potential.

Observation 2: Regarding power and the ability to showcase power: In a two point system, there would be immense power at one point, ultimately creating irrecoverable imbalance.

Nobody ever said, "I have too much power and I would love to give it away."

This immense accumulation of power provides access to the concept of GOD as an existence with a form. However we must note that every entity,

no matter how powerful, is always a step below another entity with a much higher power.

For example: Human beings are more powerful than animals, the perceived nature is more powerful than human beings, planets are more powerful than perceived nature, stars are more powerful than planets and this continues. Therefore, the influence is never static, influence changes on every correction and at every level. This is the reason we personify GOD, rather than frame the picture of "THE" GOD.

2.1 Dealing with the Coincidence conundrum

Coincidences doesn't exist in the TBR method because of the way multiple systems can be connected; correction in one system will affect other systems.

The mention of a coincidence is nothing but an incidence that was waiting to happen, based on proximity or affinity, that brought about a change in one system, affecting other systems.

The idea of chance simply doesn't exist while using the TBR method, everything is a choice based on proximity or affinity. There are no parallels here.

A parallel existence of three point systems can exist, and they remain parallel without affecting other parallel systems.

The figures below shows the complexity of the systems using the TBR method. Even though, some points might look insignificant, chaotic, shapeless, formless etc, a change in only one point will affect the entire system discounting the size. This is also the basis of chaos theory.

The above figure represents a simple connection of systems using the TBR method.

The above figure represents a slightly complex connection of systems with perceivable overlaps using the TBR method.

The above figure represents a chaotic yet meaningful connection of systems based on proximity using the TBR method.

The above figure represents a chaotic yet meaningful connection of systems based on affinity using the TBR method.

The above figure represents a chaotic yet meaningful connection of systems based on proximity and affinity using the TBR method.

Philosophy - "Coincidence is always a parallel, not a connection."

2.2 Understanding Entropy (ez)

In the TBR method, entropy is defined as a remainder after action. The TBR method forces a system to attain perfection even if perfection simply cannot be attained.

The strict requirement to attain a higher standard, forces the system to utilize the remainder or let the remainder pick it's course and settle; until the next self-correction of the system is triggered.

Entropy and entropic value can be used interchangeably in this system.

In the TBR method, if a glual anchor (Φ) collapses, the obligation to fill the space of the collapsed glual anchor (Φ) lies with the remaining two glual anchors (Φ). If the obligation is not met, entropy does the filling.

The entropy here can be complementary to the system, or supplementary, but the void must be filled, because there is no room for zero occupancy in the TBR method.

The above figure represents a dynamic entropic point (ez).

Philosophy - "A favourable entropy gives rise to the notion of luck, absence of favourability is called fate."

2.3 Why a triangle, not a line or a square or other shapes or point systems?

A triangle is the shortest path to realize accountability. We use triangle and triangulation interchangeably in this context.

An affect on every contributor (an active point asserting influence) in the system will effect the remaining existors (inactive points without the power to influence), this causes turbulence and avoids the need for stagnancy, because of the need for continuous work required to maintain the equilibrium by minimizing adverse effects.

In simple terms, triangulation doesn't tolerate stagnancy, because of the accountability factor.

In a two point system, the cause and effect will be limited to the narrative of either points, and there is no way anyone could truly understand and conclude with true and false values.

In a four point system and systems with more than four points, there exists a space for coalition, because of this, the deficit or surplus can be significant, causing one point to benefit from avoiding the effect.

In a three point system, narration and coalition will collapse, and only justification works, giving rise to individualities and connect the individual points to affect one another.

There is no escape in a three point system, because a change in one point will affect the remaining two points irrespective of the valuation. Tilt doesn't work in a three point system.

Hence triangulation can objectively bring about change to maintain an equilibrium. The constant check and the need for correction, with cause and effect and forced manipulation, will make the contributors contribute by evaluating the status of the construct.

Technically, existors wouldn't contribute, but the system makes the existors obligated to contribute, turning existors into contributors.

If an existor fails to contribute, the system will show an imbalance, and begins to collapse.

Therefore, the need to contribute for the sake of correction, will be based on a calculated approach, rather than charity. This makes triangulation very effective in maintaining the equilibrium, making sure nobody gets the throne and nobody settles to drone.

Philosophy - "One's disintegration is another's refill".

2.4 The goal of the TBR method

The TBR method showcases an imperfect system perfectly.

The TBR method assigns values divided equally, accounting to 33,33,33 for each glual anchor (\mathbb{Q}), with a remaining balance of 1, (or 0.3,0.3,0.3 and 0.1, on normalization) forming a perfect system, accounting to 100%, and hence, does not contain entropy.

But lack of entropy creates a system that doesn't fail, eventually normalizing existence and making everything moot.

Therefore to counter this, the remainder of 1 in the TBR method assumes the role of entropy and force-supplements any one glual anchor (\mathbb{Q}) among the three glual anchors (\mathbb{Q}) to satisfy accountability of that remaining 1 value.

This creates an imbalance in the system and acts as a trigger for self-correction of the system removing the additional 1 out of any glual anchor (\mathbb{Q}) containing an extra 1. However, the remainder 1 being entropic in nature will again randomly choose a glual anchor (\mathbb{Q}) to force-supplement for the sake of accountability, creating an imbalance, thereby retriggering self-correction of the system, and this process continues indefinitely.

The remainder here is also considered as entropic value and can be used interchangeably with entropy.

In systems driven by the TBR method, the volatility is directly proportional to the tolerance, high tolerance leads to high volatility, and low tolerance leads to low volatility.

The goal is to achieve low volatility to maintain non-destructive correction and is achieved by performing work with least effort, resulting in a Minimum Deed (represented by $\mu\Delta$).

Minimum Deed ($\mu\Delta$) is the amount of work done to perform a correction.

It is deliberately called Minimum Deed to signify the importance of the outcome of the TBR method. Meaning, any work done in a system using the TBR method is considered the least amount of work done, and one could always do better, qualitatively or quantitatively, depending on the requirements of the system.

A system close to perfection can be achieved with minimal energy loss when the tolerance is set to 0 (semantically speaking).

The goal is to achieve close to equilibrium by performing work with minimum effort and maximum effect.

Minimum Deed is directly proportional to volatility, and also inversly proportional to efficiency of a system.

A system should aim to keep the minimum deed value to the lowest benchmark based on study and research of the system, any value above the system benchmark points to an increase in volatility of the system.

The required inputs for the TBR method to work are,

The value of all three glual anchors (\mathcal{Q}) at any given capture.

Let's call them,

$$P1, P2, P3 \tag{1}$$

where the above are initial measures of three glual anchors (\mathcal{Q}).

We will also capture the highest value among $P1$, $P2$ and $P3$ and call it,

$$P_{mv} \tag{2}$$

where the above is the most volatile among $P1$, $P2$ and $P3$.

We then normalize measures of $P1$, $P2$ and $P3$ by finding the ratio of the $P1$, $P2$, $P3$ and P_{mv} to a maximum value making sure the output is anywhere between 0 and 1, giving us,

$$P1w, P2w, P3w, Pmw \tag{3}$$

Then, we find the travel time from initial captured positions of $P1$, $P2$ and $P3$ to the threshold position set by the system.

Let's call them

$$TtP1, TtP2, TtP3 \tag{4}$$

where the above values are travel times of $P1$, $P2$ and $P3$ respectively.

We will also capture the travel time of the most volatile among $P1$, $P2$ and $P3$ and call it,

$$TtP_{mv} \quad (5)$$

where the above value is the travel time of the most volatile P_{mv} .

To obtain the values of $TtP1$, $TtP2$, $TtP3$, TtP_{mv} , we perform the following operation,

$$TtP1 = TbP1 - TaP1 \quad (6)$$

where $TaP1$ is time at initial capture position, $TbP1$ is the time at the threshold position of $P1$.

$$TtP2 = TbP2 - TaP2 \quad (7)$$

where $TaP2$ is time at initial capture position, $TbP2$ is the time at the threshold position of $P2$.

$$TtP3 = TbP3 - TaP3 \quad (8)$$

where $TaP3$ is time at initial capture position, $TbP3$ is the time at the threshold position of $P3$.

$$TtP_{mv} = TbP_{mv} - TaP_{mv} \quad (9)$$

where TaP_{mv} is time at initial capture position, TbP_{mv} is the time at the threshold position of P_{mv} .

We then normalize the travel times by finding the ratio of the $TtP1$, $TtP2$, $TtP3$ and TtP_{mv} to the maximum value making sure the output is anywhere

between 0 and 1, giving us,

$$TtP1_w, TtP2_w, TtP3_w, TtP_{mvw} \quad (10)$$

where the above inputs are travel times of $P1_w$, $P2_w$, $P3_w$ and P_{mvw} respectively.

We then add the travel time of $P1_w$, $P2_w$, and $P3_w$,

$$TtP_w = \sum_{i=1}^3 TtPi_w \quad (11)$$

Now, we have the following required input values,

$$P1_w, P2_w, P3_w, P_{mvw} \quad (12)$$

$$TtP1_w, TtP2_w, TtP3_w, TtP_{mvw}, TtP_w \quad (13)$$

Now substituting the above values in the equations below,

$$\mu\Delta = \frac{(\mu e \times f_{\max}^2)}{100} \quad (14)$$

where $\mu\Delta$ is minimum Deed, μe is minimum Effort, and f_{\max} is Maximum effect.

To obtain the value of minimum Effort,

$$\mu e = \frac{P_{mvw}}{TtP_{mvw}} \quad (15)$$

where μe is minimum Effort, P_{mvw} is the normalized value of the measure of the most volatile glual anchor (\mathbb{Q}) and TtP_{mvw} is the normalized value of the travel time of most volatile glual anchor (\mathbb{Q}).

To obtain the value of Maximum effect (f_{\max}),

$$f_{\max} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^3 Pi_w}{TtP_w} \quad (16)$$

where f_{\max} is Maximum effect, $\sum_{i=1}^3 P_i w$ is the sum of normalized initial measure of all glual anchors (\mathbb{Q}) and TtP_w is the sum of normalized travel times of all glual anchors (\mathbb{Q}).

Proportionality:

$$\mu\Delta \propto S_v \propto 1/S_e \quad (17)$$

where $\mu\Delta$ is minimum Deed, S_v is system volatility and S_e is System efficiency.

The time taken to approach lowest volatility (0 tolerance) from random volatility (high tolerance) also determines the weakness of the glual anchor (\mathbb{Q}) and ultimately the system.

Triggers for self-correction:

1. Change in valuation at any glual anchor (\mathbb{Q}) that brings about imbalance by not totalling to 99.
2. Change in the valuation of the limiting / gating glual anchor (\mathbb{Q}) when the value goes below the remainder or entropic value.

2.5 Glual anchor(s) (Φ)

Glual anchors (Φ) used in the TBR method are placeholders to store the values of building blocks of a known infinite system. A glual anchor (Φ) is a dynamic anchor that works as both contextual and a global anchor.

The above figure represents the symbol designed to highlight the dynamic nature of glual anchors.

The free-inlet at the top representing the opening for affinity, the closed loop representing containment for proximity, and the edge at the right bottom corner of the loop representing provision for entropy.

The prerequisite for a work completion request expected from an intelligent system - is the context of the request.

If a system is asked to complete a task - stating the expectations, the reason for request, scope of work, or hundred different reasons specific to the context of the task becomes essential, from which an intelligent system proceeds to create a Φ based on the context to perform a function or execute a task.

The absence of context leads to confusion and questions the purpose of the task, and this applies only to intelligent systems.

In the absence of a context, the intelligent system will automatically create contexts and assign temporary Φ for the sake of completion of the task, this assumption will lead to creation of temporary Φ in huge numbers or at least two.

Why at least two? Because a system using the TBR method needs at least

two \mathcal{Q} , the third \mathcal{Q} will be defined by the observer, usually a limiter / gate and will not be replaced.

The above figure represents the positioning of \mathcal{Q} . The top \mathcal{Q} is usually fixed by the observer, or the owner (L/G - Limiter/Gate). The bottom two \mathcal{Q} will assume the values based on proximity, affinity in context or out-of-context (Proximity/Affinity-Contextual/Global).

Now when the system creates hundreds or thousands of temporary \mathcal{Q} , we reduce all the created temporary \mathcal{Q} to two \mathcal{Q} in the TBR method.

This reduction will help us simplify the temporary \mathcal{Q} based on priority, thereby minimizing the complexity of having many temporary \mathcal{Q} .

The system at any given time will contain at least one temporary \mathcal{Q} if not two, depending on whether the observer provides \mathcal{Q} or not.

Also, this reduction will not doctor the outcome. The reduction here should not be confused with deduction, subtraction or elimination. The reduction is strictly based on priority.

For example, if the number of temporary \mathcal{Q} created by the system is 100, we reduce this to 1 temporary \mathcal{Q} + a group of 99 temporary \mathcal{Q} , totalling to 2 \mathcal{Q} .

Further, one of the Φ will be based on the context of the work, and relates to the task provider or requestor, this anchor will be in alignment with the needs of the observer, the global Φ is based on everything else, that does not directly relate to the observer.

The system is then allowed to perform a task and the result is captured.

2.6 Rules

1. All three Φ must be occupied.
2. The main Φ is the limiting or gating Φ with the valuation to never go below the entropic value or the remainder.

Philosophy - "One cannot have a list of priorities, one can only pick a priority from a list."

Achieving a goal of zero tolerance might sound absurd. But it's not a linear effect, therefore, the harshness of zero tolerance depends on the weakness of the system.

Ultimately, the ability to implement the TBR method relies on the guts and confidence of the observer. Hence, the limiting / gating \mathbb{Q} plays an important role in determining the status of the observer mindset.

The limiter here promotes thinking in terms of threshold and containment. Understanding threshold and containment without inflicting harm to the self or others, avoiding potential adversities and decreasing liabilities, the observer must think and reason with honesty about the limitation before implementing the TBR method.

3 Conclusion

The Spin Resonance Capture (SRC) system will prove invaluable when measuring a paradigm with unknown infinities, I am yet to understand it's application in a paradigm with known infinities.

The functioning of the SRC system is similar to an MRI machine, and could be considered a dumbed-down version of MRI technology at the first glance. However, it should be noted that the SRC system was developed to capture the essence of an event, and not imaging the event. This distinction makes SRC a valuable instrument to study any paradigm with unknown infinities.

My contemplation about the movement and momentum in the universe brought me to a realization, which later manifested into the TBR method. The only reason the TBR method exists is to prove the spin is real, and not imaginary. And yes, the TBR method proves it and eliminates the need for assumption in the SRC system.

Also, please note that the calculation of the Minimum Deed in the TBR method is a by-product of my exploration in trying to understand spin, so take it with a grain of salt, and I will continue to work on it, given that I am alive, healthy and entropy favours my existence. However, the TBR method conclusively proves that the spin does exist and the reason behind the spin

is a simple three point system in action.

And finally, the TBR method can be used independently from the SRC system. And even though the SRC system need not show the implementation of the TBR method; the TBR method continues to exist in the SRC system.

4 Call to Action

I invite the community to explore the presented ideas further, replicate the diagrams and concepts in their own work, and contribute new insights to deepen our collective understanding. I encourage you to ask as many questions as you want, and please do not interpret any delay in answering questions as disinterest.

I am not a native English speaker, and I have not used AI to avoid presenting this finding without receiving an acknowledgement. Hence, I request you to let me know if you find grammatical errors, spelling mistakes, syntax errors etc, and I will be glad to revise the literature.

Feel free to contact me: [protagnic\[at\]gmail\[dot\]com](mailto:protagnic[at]gmail[dot]com)

5 References

My journey towards understanding the reason for all the movement and momentum in the universe brought me to the above realizations and epiphany.

I have not referred to other papers, articles or books to arrive at this conclusion. If there are, I am an ignorant person who reinvented the wheel, but I still did it from my perspective without an external influence. I couldn't get rid of a constant standing resonance in my head asking why the spin?, and this is the result.

To prove the working of the SRC system, I developed a psychological assessment instrument with a proprietary algorithm that performs stateless alignment. It's like google maps to a person's subconscious, you get an idea of who you are dealing with even before you start the journey. If you are

curious about the website, visit: <https://psynormic.com>.

6 Use case

The SRC system can be used effectively in counseling, to understand favourability, to develop based on sentimentality, fixing deep rooted psychological issues, anger management, to deal with insecurities, to detect feasibility etc.

The TBR method can be effectively used anywhere with known weights and measures.

You might have noticed that I continued after conclusion. Technically, there is no conclusion, there is only transformation.

With that said, I will tentatively end this paper with one last philosophy that made me write this paper.

Philosophy - "Civility is the triangulation of humanity."